

ATTAMANIRBHAR BHARAT (SELF REALIANT INDIA) AN OPPORTUNITY IN THE MIDST OF THE COVID STORM

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Abstract:

The frighteningly memorable year 2020 that aggrandized the influence of China- born Covid-19 to global demographic landscape, not just human life but it even placed the global economy in jeopardy. City roads everywhere wore deserted looks and social life was replaced by the unconventional norm of social distancing.

Finding itself in this swim or sink situation, India under the dynamic leadership of Prime Minister Modi chose to embark itself on the path of the “Attama nirbhar Bharat, self-reliant India”. Thus, India chose to take the bull by the horns and started exploring the opportunities in the midst of the covid storm.

Accordingly, the five pillars of making India self-reliant were chalked out by the present dispensation. Correspondingly, the economic package was announced along with the various packages released during the lockdown period to the tune of US\$ 283.73 billion, which was about 10 per cent of India's GDP. It was meant to provide support and strength to various sections of the country and give a renewed boost to the development journey of the country in 2020.

The researcher by hypothesis has expressed apprehensions about the future trajectory of this movement. The researcher believes that the success of this movement depends upon the various factors like bipartisan approach, pro-growth tendency and focus on infrastructure.

An attempt has been made by this proposed paper to realise that the success of this movement is in the hands of the people and not the govt. The govt can start but it has to be turned into a grand success by the citizenry.

Introduction

The frighteningly memorable year 2020 that aggrandized the influence of China born Covid-19 to global demographic landscape is as catastrophic as doomsday scenario plot of any science fiction-based Hollywood movie. It took the whole world aback. Not just human life but it even placed the global economy in jeopardy. City roads everywhere wore deserted looks and social life was replaced by the unconventional norm of social distancing. The political big guns from the former US. President Trump to the British Prime Minister Boris Johnson all fell prey to corona. To defeat the darkness of this despair, all the nation states were doing their level best to accelerate their vaccine development programme. Finding itself in this swim or sink situation, India under the dynamic leadership of the Prime Minister Modi chose to embark itself on the path of the “Attama nirbhar Bharat, self-reliant India”. Thus, India chose to take the bull by the horns and started exploring the opportunities in the midst of the covid storm.

The meat of the matter:

Accordingly, the five pillars of making India self-reliant were chalked out by the present dispensation:

- **Economy:** We have to bring an economy that doesn't bring incremental change but quantum jump.
- **Infrastructure:** We need an infrastructure which can become the identity of modern India.

- **System:** A system that doesn't follow norms of the previous century. It should be able to fulfil our 21st century dreams and be technology driven.
- **Vibrant Democracy:** It is our strength; it is the source of energy for our dream to make India self-reliant.
- **Demand:** The demand-supply chain is our power; we should use it to its full potential.

Correspondingly, the economic package was announced along with the various packages released during the lockdown period to the tune of US\$ 283.73 billion, which was about 10 per cent of India's GDP. It was meant to provide support and strength to various sections of the country and give a renewed boost to the development journey of the country in 2020.

Consequently, land, labour, liquidity and laws were highlighted in this package to strengthen our commitment to realize our vision of the self-reliant India.

On this clarion call of the Prime Minister, India also swiftly adapted itself to this new normal situation and manufactured 2 lakh PPE kits and 2 lakh N95 masks. The PPE kit industry grew to become 7000 crore sector in two months (next to China) which were never on our manufacturing priority list earlier.

Another milestone was that the largest fund in the country worth ₹21,000 crore (US\$2.9 billion) was setup by the IIT Alumni Council with the aim of supporting the mission towards self-reliance.

One of the watershed moments was that India banned 59 Chinese apps for security reasons and found many local companies sprang up overnight to fill the vacuum like: TikTok, Helo, Big Libe, Vigo Video, Vmate, U Video and Kwai were replaced by Indian apps like Mitron, Bolo Indya, Roposo, Dubsmash

India's own 'Made in India' 5G network was also announced in July 2020 by Reliance Jio, using 100 per cent home grown technologies and solutions".

Similarly, for the first time, in July 2020, Apple announced to manufacturer one of their premium iPhone models in India.

Recently, Tesla setup its plant in Bangalore to roll out the battery driven cars and trucks.

Furthermore, the defence sector also saw a phenomenal rise in defence spending in response to the Chinese attempt to invade the buffer land between the two Asian giants. New Défense investment were put in place to turn India from the major importer to the exporter of defense products. Today, India is in position to supply defence equipments to the 40 countries.

Hypothesis:

The idea of self-reliant India has always been the driving force behind the transformation of the citizenry's thought process. Gandhiji's call to boycott foreign goods to the Nationalisation of Indian Industries till the decade of 80's, all such moves ignited the feeling of nationalism in the country; but ignored the relevance of economy. Today, in the era of globalisation, the writer believes that the Attamanirbhar Bharat is not just another National Movement but the programme that is meant make our economy more competitive globally. India has demographic advantage to become the power centre of global economy.

A) Dragon and Elephant can dance together but the Elephant can out-dance dragon:

India's next door neighbour China is all set to become the largest economy of the world and has been using debt trap diplomacy. The recent example of China taking over the Hanbandota Sea port from Srilanka for its failure to repay debts to China is a good case in point.

India in this scenario can't wait and watch but has to leapfrog by removing trade barriers and promoting investment in export-oriented sectors of economy. Its golden time for India, as the world is upset with China for hiding the facts related to the Covid-19 and its expansionist designs in South China Sea.

Recently, the Chinese envoy named Sun Weidong commenting on the ongoing Ladakh faceoff between Indian and Chinese soldiers said that “the realization of Dragon and Elephant dancing together is the only right choice for China and India. On economic front, we have to prove this that although the Dragon and Elephant can dance together but the Elephant can out-dance dragon as proved by our forces in Ladakh. India must expedite its processes to capitalize on this anti-china scenario and accelerate its economic growth.

B) Bipartisan:

This national movement for its all-round success needs bipartisan approach. It shouldn't be the baby of ruling party; it must enjoy the support of the principal opposition party as well. The bipartisan approval will strengthen the faith of the foreign investors and would avoid the scenario of uncertainty. Bipartisan approach assures that the principal opposition party (after coming to power) wouldn't come up with the draconian laws to fizzle it out in the future.

In other words, the political consensus is the precondition to its success.

C) Overcome Anti-Growth Mind-set:

Another approach to this movement, is overcoming the anti-growth mind-set of our citizenry. This anti-growth tendency was demonstrated by us during the time, when we signed the TRIPS agreement. The recent example is the three farm laws passed by our parliament. The writer believes that the media, the govt and the NGOs together must educate the people to mould their thought process to promote growth. Let's not forget, the prosperous India with global clout is in the interest of every Indian. The founding fathers of our constitution have created the powerful judiciary that is capable to protect our rights and therefore, we don't need to be insecure with the policies that accelerate growth.

D) Infrastructure:

The focus on upgrading our infrastructure will keep this movement undying. The foreign investors want better roads, transport connectivity with ports to send their products abroad. The transit mechanism should be less complex and more time efficient.

Conclusion:

The writer refuses to accept this mission merely as a roadmap to recovery in the post unlock period, it is much more than that. It's a national movement, which shouldn't lose momentum given the demographic size of our great nation. The surging India with the ideals of “Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam” (World is one family) express our divine intention of serving the world. India's vibrant cultural practises like yoga & ayurveda have already demonstrated the same.

Recently, we embarked ourselves on the path of harnessing solar energy by forming International Solar Alliance. This reflects India's sincerity towards reversing the scenario of global warming and climate change as our dependence on the hydro-carbons will be replaced by solar energy in the future.

Moreover, the New Education Policy also has been designed to accomplish this vision. The main thrust of this policy is to turn our students into globally competitive personnel equipped with the skills to produce the state of art technologies that could turn our great nation into the technology hub and the power centre of the service sector.

The Indian intellectuality sitting in the Silicon Valley helped the world to overcome the millennium bug crisis in the decade of 2000s. Now, it's time to invest our brain power into the growth of our economy by modernizing the supply chain. Besides that, we need to consistently monitor the Scheme called "Aajivika", the economic package to our cottage industry, home industry, medium industry, which means millions of people will be pulled out of the poverty and would promote the local products (Vocal for local).

Furthermore, the three farm laws namely, The **Farmers'** Produce Trade and Commerce (Promotion and Facilitation) **Act (2020)**, The Essential Commodities (Amendment) **Act (2020)** and The **Farmers** (Empowerment and Protection) Agreement on Price Assurance and **Farm Services Act (2020)** will empower our farmers to have more bargaining power and will increase investment in the farming sector. It will also help us to strengthen our supply chain even in the agrarian sector of our economy.

Thus, the stage look set for India to make rapid strides in acquiring its rightful place in the world.

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